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(<http://www.megalab.gr>)

New: Symposium Programme Announced (click here)
(http://conference2017.monubasin.com/images/Monubasin_conf_program_v1.pdf)

☰ Committees (http://conference2017.monubasin.com/index.php?option=com_sppagebuilder&view=page&i)

- (/)
- ≡ Program (http://conference2017.monubasin.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1)
 - ≡ Authors guidelines (<http://conference2017.monubasin.com/index.php/conference/authors-guidelines>)
 - ≡ Registration details (<http://conference2017.monubasin.com/index.php/conference/registration-details>)
 - ↗ Submission System (<https://easychair.org/conferences/?conf=monubasin2017>)
 - Ⓜ Registration system (<https://www.eventora.com/en/Events/10th-monubasin>)
 - ≡ Access to NTUA (<http://conference2017.monubasin.com/index.php/conference/venue-2>)

10th MONUBASIN "Natural and Anthropogenic Hazards and Sustainable Preservation"

This **International Symposium on the Conservation of Monuments in the Mediterranean Basin (MONUBASIN)** has provided a forum for scientists, technicians and experts, in the area conservation and restoration of monuments, to present their work and exchange ideas and experiences for over **28 years**.

In this context, we have the great pleasure to announce that the **National Technical University Athens (NTUA, School of Chemical Engineering, Material Science and Engineering Section) will be organizing the 10th MONUBASIN.**

The Symposium will take place from **20 to 22 of September 2017** following previous symposia Bari (1989), Geneva (1991), Venice (1994), Rhodes (1997), Seville (2000), Lisbon (2004), Orléans (2007), Patras (2010) and Ankara (2014).

The theme of this Symposium is "**Natural and Anthropogenic Hazards and Sustainable Preservation**" and refers to the natural and anthropogenic hazards on monuments, as well as the technologies used for damage rehabilitation in the direction of sustainable, long-lasting preservation.

The Symposium addresses research work from restoration engineers, architects, geologists, restorers and conservators of stone artifacts and other specialists in the decay and restoration of monuments, as well as archaeologists, art historians and scientists in the fields of physics, chemistry and biology.

During the 10th Symposium, the **Monubasin Digital Repository (MDR)** will be presented to the participants. The MDR will offer access to all previous Symposiums' proceedings (more than 900 papers) providing various methods of search (e.g. full-text search, by author name, by paper title by Symposium, etc.). All Symposium participants will have free access to the MDR contents.

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Symposium Language

The official Language of the Symposium is English.

10th International Symposium
on the Conservation of Monuments
in the Mediterranean Basin

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Important dates

- 17/10/2016 **Conference Announcement**
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31/5/2016 **Abstract submission deadline**
30/06/2017 **Full papers submission deadline**
07/09/2017 **Early registration deadline**
30/08/2017 **Symposium programme
announcement**
20/09/2017 **Symposium starting day**

Call for Extended Abstracts - Papers (Deadline: until end of May)

Authors are requested to submit extended abstracts on the following topics, after studying carefully Authors Guidelines.

1. Technologies for Damage Rehabilitation and Sustainable Preservation
2. Methodologies for Characterization and Damage Assessment
3. Historical and Structural Aspects of Monuments
4. Natural and Anthropogenic Damage Hazards
5. Digital Techniques for Cultural Heritage
6. Planning and Cultural Heritage Management

From Our Blog

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(/index.php/conference
/blog/81-announcing-the-

(/index.php/conference
/blog/79-things-to-do-in-

programme-announcement-30-8-2017)

29 August 2017

Symposium Programme Announcement (30/8/2017) (/index.php/conference/blog/83-symposium-programme-announcement-30-8-2017)

venue-for-the-41st-elag-conference-2)

29 January 2017

2nd Announcement & Abstract deadline extension (end of May, 2017) (/index.php/conference/blog/81-announcing-the-venue-for-the-41st-elag-conference-2)

athens)

13 January 2017

Things to Do in Athens (/index.php/conference/blog/79-things-to-do-in-athens)

Event Organisers

National Technical University of Athens
School of Chemical Engineering
Department of Material Science and Engineering

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HELLENIC REPUBLIC
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